

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Mabrouka company	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Potato	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

Fill the questionnaire so a Cost-Benefit Analysis can be developed. **Use approximations and annual averages** to fill the information. Fill the questionnaire **indicating data for last year and the present year, if available.**

PRESENT STATUS

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m3 or analogous*)

Around 7 020 m3/ ha

2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

6 liters of fuel/hour

For potato around 65 hours of irrigation

3. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

256 \$ during potato period

4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

1 labor for 4 months of work (permanent) (11.5\$/day)

15 labors for 7 days (5.5\$/day) + transport fees (230\$)

15 labors for 15 days (5.5 \$/day) + transport fees (493\$)

24 hours of machineries work (111 liters of fuel)

5. Average cost of labor

Ranging between 5.5 and 11.5 \$/ day

6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Organic manure	37.5 tons	(6 \$/kg)
Di-ammonium Phosphate (DAP)	300kg	(14.8 \$/50kg)
Potassium nitrate	400kg	(65 \$/25kg)
Ammonium nitrate	800 kg/ha	(12.5 \$/ 50kg)
Calcium	150 kg	(38 \$/25kg)
Magnesium	150 kg	(24.6 \$/25kg)
NPK (13-40-13)	700 kg	(72 \$/25kg)

7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Insecticide (Delfos)	50 kg/ha	(8.8 \$/ kg)
Mospilan	600 g	(38 \$/0.25kg)
Fungicide (agroxide)	4 kg	(9.8 \$/kg)
Lannate	3.5 kg	(31 \$/kg)

8. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

He uses his own machineries

9. Yield per hectare per annum (*total kg and €/kg*)

24 t/ha

- 80% of the production is sold as seeds (625 \$/tons)
- 20% is sold for consumption (197 \$/tons)

Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m3 or analogous*)

Around 5033 m3/ha

11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

576 instead of 780 liters during potato cycle

12. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

200 \$ instead of 256 \$

13. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

He expected 3 hours reduction /week

14. Average cost of labor

The same according to the farmer

15. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

The same according to the farmer

16. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same according to the farmer

17. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same according to the farmer

18. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

He expected a small yield reduction (5%) with this water reduction

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Salem Aloui	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Potato	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

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PRESENT STATUS

19. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m3 or analogous*)

Around 4800 m3/ ha

20. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

8 kw/h

For potato around 36 hours of irrigation

21. Average annualized price paid for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

1180 \$/year for all the exploitation

22. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

10 labor for 15 days

3 hours for machinery

23. Average cost of labor

8 \$/ day

24. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Organic manure 10 tons (15 \$ /ton)

Ammonium nitrate 100kg /ha (6.5 \$/kg)

Potassium nitrate 60kg/ha (65 \$/25kg)

25. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Fungicide 5 kg/ha (6.5 \$/ kg)

26. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

10 \$/h

27. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

22 t/ ha (0.32 \$/kg)

*Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water*

28. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

Around 4000 m³/ha

29. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

240 kw (11 \$) instead of 288 (13.5 \$) during potato cycle

30. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

240 kw (11 \$)

31. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

The same according to the farmer

32. Average cost of labor

The same according to the farmer

33. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

The same according to the farmer

34. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same according to the farmer

35. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same according to the farmer

36. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

He think that yield will be reduced by around 10%

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Jomaa Dhibi	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Citrus	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

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PRESENT STATUS

37. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

Around 7020 m³/ ha

38. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

15 kw/h

39. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

3648 \$/year for all the exploitation

Around 20% for citrus

40. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

2 labors for 14 days for planting

1 labor for pruning (197 \$ for each season)

1 Permanent labor (3 months per year was dedicated for citrus (328 \$/month))

3 hours for machinery

41. Average cost of labor

8.5 \$/ day

42. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Organic manure: 15 tons (his own Organic manure)

Ammonium nitrate: (13 \$/50kg)

Phosphoric acid : 100 liter (3 \$/30kg)

Calcium: 50 kg (39 \$/ 25kg)

Magnesium: 50 kg (24 \$/25kg)

Fer: 10 kg (16.5 \$/kg)

Manganese: 30 liter (8 \$/ l)

Boron: 5 liter (8 \$/ l)

Gibberellic acid : 5 capsule (3 \$/capsule)

Amino acid : 10 liter (13 \$/l)

43. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Mineuse (miner) : 3 liter (148 \$/ 3l)

Insecticide : 3 l/ha (33 \$/3l)

44. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

He has his own tractor

45. Yield per hectare per annum (*total kg and €/kg*)

Low production since the orchard recently enter in production and also due to others environmental factors

Around 2.5 t/ha (0.980 \$/ kg)

*Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water*

46. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

Around 5033 m³/ha

47. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

720 kw instead of 1000 kw/year for citrus

48. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

288 \$ instead of 391 \$/year for citrus irrigation

49. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

Can be reduced by 1 hour of work /week

50. Average cost of labor

The same according to the farmer

51. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

The same according to the farmer

52. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same according to the farmer

53. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same according to the farmer

54. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

He expected no significant yield reduction (4%)

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Lamine Moussa	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Citrus	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

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PRESENT STATUS

55. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

8220 m³ /ha

56. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

20 kw/h

57. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

1770 \$/year

58. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

1 labor for 10 days for weeding

Others activities are conducted by farmer

Machinery (6 h)

59. Average cost of labor

Labor 8 \$/ day

60. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Only organic amendment was considered in this farm

Compost was determined on the basis of biomass and nettle manure

3 to 4 kg per tree

Mineral nutrition 1 kg (16 \$)

61. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Only biological treatment was considered which is prepared by farmer

62. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

8 \$/ hour

63. Yield per hectare per annum (*total kg and €/kg*)

1.6 ton/ha (0.85 \$/kg)

Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water

64. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

6886 m³/ha

65. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

4800 kw/year instead of 5760 kw/year for citrus

66. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

221 \$/ year instead of 265 \$/year for citrus crop

67. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

The same according to the farmer

68. Average cost of labor

The same according to the farmer

69. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

The same according to the farmer

70. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same according to the farmer

71. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same according to the farmer

72. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

Around 4% yield reduction

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Mohamed Bouzidi	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Potato	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

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PRESENT STATUS

73. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m3 or analogous*)

Around 5830 m3/ ha

74. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

12 kw/h

For potato around 52 hours of irrigation

75. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

1642 \$/year for all the exploitation

76. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

26 labors

24 hours of animal work

77. Average cost of labor

6.5 \$/ day

78. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Organic manure: 20 tons (15 t is about 200 \$)

Ammonium nitrate: 100 kg/ha (6.5 \$/kg)

Phosphoric acid: 60 kg/ha (3 \$/30kg)

Potassium: 250 kg (24.5 \$/25kg)

79. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Fungicide: 5 kg/ha (6.5 \$/ kg)

Insecticide 3 l/ha (33 \$/3l)

80. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

NA

81. Yield per hectare per annum (*total kg and €/kg*)

10 t/ha (0.328 \$/kg)

Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water

82. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

Around 3880 m³/ha during potato cropping cycle

83. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

He will use 420 kw (16.5 \$) instead of 624 (24.6 \$)

84. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

420 kw (16.5 \$)

85. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

The same in his opinion

86. Average cost of labor

The same in his opinion

87. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

The same in his opinion

88. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same in his opinion

89. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same in his opinion

90. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

Not notably affected (7%)

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Nourddine Rojbanie	Country	Tunisia
Crop	Potato	Investigator name	Fathia Elmokh Fatma Aribi
Date	08/05/2023		

Fill the questionnaire so a Cost-Benefit Analysis can be developed. **Use approximations and annual averages** to fill the information. Fill the questionnaire **indicating data for last year and the present year, if available.**

PRESENT STATUS

91. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m3 or analogous*)

Around 6 000 m3/ ha during potato season

92. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

11 kw/h

For potato around 48 hours of irrigation

93. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

1824 \$/year for all the exploitation

94. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

2 labors for 18 days of work

1 labor for 30 days permanent labor

16 hours for machineries

95. Average cost of labor

6.5 \$/ day

96. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Organic manure: 15 tons (his own Organic manure)/ if we estimate the price of 15 t is about 200\$

Ammonium nitrate: 150 kg/ha (6.5 \$/kg)

Phosphoric acid: 60 kg/ha (3 \$/30kg)

97. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

Fungicide: 5kg/ha (6.5 \$/kg)

Insecticide: 3 l/ha (33 \$/3l)

98. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

10 \$/h

99. Yield per hectare per annum (*total kg and €/kg*)

23 t/ha (0.23 \$/kg)

*Now suppose you can have an **annual 20% improvement** in saving excess water*

100. Water use per hectare/per annum (*m³ or analogous*)

Around 5000 m³/ha

101. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (*Kw/h or analogous*)

The hour of pumping will be reduced by around half hour for each application but the number of kw /h will be the same 11 kw/h

102. Average annualized price payed for energy (*\$/Kw/h or analogous*)

Around 400 kw (15 \$) during potato cycle instead of 520 kw (20 \$)

103. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (*hours worked or analogous*). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs.

The same in his opinion

104. Average cost of labor

The same in his opinion

105. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*)

Same thing for fertilizer

106. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (*kg used & cost per kg*).

The same in his opinion

107. Cost of 1 hour of machine work

The same in his opinion

108. Yield per hectare per annum (*sold kg and €/kg*)

He think that the yield will not notably affected (5%)

2017	<i>Wet year</i>											
2018	<i>Wet year</i>											
2019				2D	2C+2D	2A +4C+4D	2A+4B +4C+4D	2A+4B +4C+4D				
2020				2A+2D	2A +2C+2D	2A +4C+4D	2A+5B +5C+5D	2A+5B +5C+5D				
2021				3A+3B +3C+3D	3A+5B +5C+5D	3A +7C+7D	3A+7B +7C+7D	3A+7B +7C+7D				

112. For each action identified in question2; what is the associated cost (for the manager) for each type of event?

Please provide as much explanation of the costs as needed. Now fill the table for your case (add rows if needed).¹

Action	Costs	Costs per episode
Stop using tower water for irrigation purpose (reduce areas cultivated by vegetable crops)	- Control visit cost - Awareness raising days and field visit cost	-10.000 dollar – 2019-2021 -8.000 dollar +5000 euro – 2019 - 2021
Reinforcing the supplement irrigation programs (olive crop)	-Subsidized water for irrigation cost -Subsidization for building water harvesting wells and reservoirs cost	460.000 – 2019,2020,2021 800.000 (2019) 120.000 (2020) 110.000 (2021)
sensitizing farmers for the rationalization of water use (water restriction)	- Awareness raising campaign cost	-5000 dollar – 2019,2020,2021
introducing water saving techniques (localized irrigation system)	- promote the adoption of water-saving techniques cost - Water saving techniques subsidies costs	-5000 dollar – 2019,2020-2021 2.400.000 – (800.000 per year)

¹ Dr. Samir answers for aggregated annual values

